

Length of arc joining two ends of diameter is always greater than the diameter in semi-circle.

Arjun Dahal^{ab}

a = Mental Asylum of Education

b = Tribhuvan University

Abstract: Circles are amazing objects in regular geometry. Through this paper, we report that the length of arc in a semi-circle joining two ends of diameter is always greater than the diameter, with experimental verification, whereas theoretical calculations show contradiction.

Keywords: Circle, Semi-Circle, Arc Diameter

Introduction:

Line of diameter passes from center of circle to two ends in circumference of circle. Let us consider three circles.

fig: a

fig:b

fig: c

In the above figures, straight line AB represents the diameter, and it divides the circles in two semi-circles.

We know,

$$\text{Circumference of circle} = 2\pi r$$

$$\text{Circumference of semi-circle} = \pi r$$

Therefore, length of arc of AB = circumference of circle - diameter

$$= \pi r - 2r$$

$$= r(\pi - 2)$$

$$= 1.14 \times r \text{ (Value of } \pi \text{ is taken as 3.14)}$$

From above result, it becomes clear that length of arc AB is less than the diameter, and it takes the form of inequality $d > 1.14 r > r$.

From figures

Length of Diameter AB	Length of Arc AB	Remarks

Angle made by diameter with arc:

We have one straight line (diameter), joining two points of arc in any curve to make two angles. Our hypothesis claims those angles to be equal, and is equal to the angles formed below the diameter. That means angles formed by diameter above and below the joints in arc of circles are equal.

Conclusion:

Thus from above calculations, contradictions can be studied in theoretical value and experimentally observed value. In theoretical calculations length of diameter is greater than that of arc, whereas experimentally observed values show that length of arc is greater than that of diameter, and inequality becomes; length of arc > diameter > radius.

References:

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